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Expert Insights: Advancing Effective Monitoring and Evaluation Methods

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Successfully trialling and implementing interventions to address critical global health issues, such as iron deficiency in women, requires diverse interest-holders to **plan, monitor** and **evaluate** key outcomes¹. Monitoring and evaluation should occur during and after the trial to accurately assess the success and sustainability of the intervention and its implementation. However, this process is often challenged by limited resources, inadequate reporting systems, and weak technical coordination¹. To better understand the factors influencing successful trial planning and monitoring and evaluating outcomes, we surveyed interest-holders committed to advancing women's health and developing sustainable solutions to tackle iron deficiency and poor nutrition. The **purpose** of this knowledge mobilisation activity is to report insights on best practices that ensure monitoring and evaluation methods are effective.

Sample	Experts-by-experience: researchers, graduate students, NGO project managers, youth & community health advocates, economists, and industry impact directors
Phenomenon of interest	Insights and perspectives on factors and approaches influencing successful trial assessments in Benin
Design	Structured survey informed by academic literature and insights from the Alliance Against Iron Deficiency working group to ensure rigor and relevance of the survey questions
Evaluation	Qualitative thematic analysis of surveys to uncover key themes and practical recommendations
Research type	Qualitative, focused on exploring applied and experiential knowledge of experts-by-experience
Outcome	Inform effective monitoring and evaluation approaches for community-based research trials

Recommendations for successful monitoring and evaluation of community-based trials

In community and cross-culture settings, monitoring and evaluation (M&E) face additional challenges compared to clinical settings. Successful and sustainable M&E require tailored approaches.

Barriers	Factors influencing the success of trial M&E:	Facilitators
Trial staff turnover	Continuity of roles: support continuous knowledge sharing, cross-training between staff, and develop a standardised documentation process to track tasks	
Turnover of community catalysts/champions	Maintain engagement: provide fair compensation and regular communication channels	
Limited participation of community leaders	Establish and maintain communication: leverage digital platforms and local networks to share programme benefits, build trust, and gather feedback to adapt approaches	
Limited availability or capacity of participants to engage	Align data collection with communities: consult community leaders on appropriate engagement times, and designate a community catalyst to coordinate data collection Maintain communication: use preferred channels to keep participants engaged	

Key people required for successful M&E:

Field coordinator	M&E manager	Community champion	Lead academic
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Team level communication strategies:

- Shared visual timelines and dashboards
- Dedicated project champion to oversee monitoring tasks
- Regular feedback loops with field agents

Recommended timeline and methods for post-trial M&E

Community catalysts

Designate and train local community catalysts to collect and report M&E data

Qualitative monitoring activities

Collect M&E data through community groups, individual interviews, group discussions, and/or community feedback sessions

Mobile data collection

Empower community health workers to collect and report M&E data using mobile tools (phone-based surveys/reporting)

Key considerations: combining methods can lead to better validity and reliability of the findings

1. Bezabih (2023) Agric Foof Secur 11:61